

Why Arrangements and their Maximization in Statistical Mechanics? Part 2

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In statistical mechanics texts, various factorial schemes related to physical configurations or arrangements are used to obtain equilibrium distributions by maximizing the \ln of the number of arrangements subject to energy and particle number constraints. For example, this is particularly performed for the Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) distributions with the maximization involving the usual derivative d/df where $f(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . In a previous note (1), we tried to map a reaction balance approach to this configuration approach. For the Fermi-Dirac case, it seems a factorial configuration approach may be meaningful, but for the boson and other generalized cases, there may be problems. In this note, we consider instead a different definition of the derivative and try to find differences that arise in an equilibrium scenario if one changes the number of particles associated with each energy e_i . The idea is that a change in $f(e_i)$ is not performed through a simple derivative because physically such a change is related to a reaction (e.g. scattering) which may have certain enhancements or restrictions as in the FD or BE cases. Thus we argue, one may not need physical configurations which mimic scattering enhancements or restrictions.

Reaction Balance

Consider an elastic two body scattering reaction $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ ((1a)) governed by:

$$g(f(e_1)) g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3)) g(f(e_4)) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and relating to ((1a)) yields $\ln(g(f(e_i))) = -(e_i-u)/T$ ((2)). For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $g=1$ while $g=f/(1-f)$ for the FD case and $g=f/(1+f)$ for the BE case.

Thus, one does not need to use factorial schemes, entropy or partition functions. It should be noted, however, that ((2)) uses averages. For example, for the FD case, a fermion is in a state e_i or not, yet one uses $f(e_i) < 1$ to describe this state.

A question arises as to how one may link reaction balance to ideas commonly used in statistical mechanics. Kaniadakis (2) establishes a link with entropy density by defining it as:

$$S_d = \int df \ln(g(f)) \quad ((3))$$

Then: $d/df S_d + d/df (e_i-u)/T f = 0$ yields ((2)).

One may then use: $E-TS+uN$ to link the above entropy to $\ln(\text{Grand partition function})$. Thus, one obtains entropy without any factorial schemes. This entropy function, however, is associated with a usual derivative, d/df . In information theory, probability for a system is given by $\exp(\text{entropy})$. It is possible that a change to $f(e_i)$, i.e. the number of particles with energy e_i

also changes reaction rates. Thus, the Kaniadakis entropy seems to be a mixture of configuration and dynamics.

A second question, however, arises as to how one may link reaction balance to factorial schemes which one often sees in statistical mechanics texts and information theory.

Factorial Schemes

In (3), the following schemes are given for the FD and BE cases:

FD Case: Consider g_i degenerate boxes for level e_i and n_i fermions with energy e_i . Then: $g_i! / [n_i! (g_i - n_i)!]$ ((4)) is the number of arrangements.

BE Case: Consider g_i degenerate boxes for level e_i and n_i bosons with energy e_i . Then: $(n_i + g_i - 1)! / [n_i! (g_i - 1)!]$ ((5)) is the number of arrangements.

Both of these arrangements involve physical configurations, but do not seem to be explicitly linked to any kind of reaction rules (enhancements or restrictions). In both cases, one finds the equilibrium distribution $n_i(e_i)$ by:

$$d/dn_i \ln(\text{number of arrangements}) - d/dn_i (e_i - u)/T n_i = 0$$

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, we argue the number of arrangements is:

$$M! / [m_1! m_2! m_3! \dots] \text{ ((6))} \quad \text{although texts give } \text{Product over } i \text{ } g_i^{n_i} / n_i!$$

Information Theory

In information theory (3), entropy is defined as:

$$\text{Probability for a system} = \exp(\text{entropy}) = 1 / (\text{number of arrangements}) \text{ ((7))}$$

Thus, using Stirling's approximation on the \ln of ((6)) (i.e, m_i are large) yields the usual Shannon's entropy:

$$\text{Probability} = \exp(\text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))) \text{ ((8))}$$

((8)) may be obtained without any use of arrangements by arguing that if one has independent $f(e_i)$ and N particles (where N is large) then $Nf(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . The probability is then: $\text{Product over } i \text{ } f(e_i)^{Nf(e_i)}$ which is the same as ((8))

Reaction Derivative Approach

Shannon's probability ((8)) may be used to find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution by using:

$$d/df f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) + (e_i - u)/T f(e_i) = 0 \quad ((9))$$

What should be done in the case of general scattering where $\ln(g(e_i)) = -(e_i - u)/T$?

Using Kaniadakis entropy density $S_d = \int df \ln(g(f))$ is one approach, but does not seem to be linked directly to factorial schemes.

We try to argue the following. No matter what $g(f)$ is, there will be an equilibrium distribution $f(e_i)$ (assuming that equilibrium may be formed). In such a case, one may consider ((6)) as being a map of the physical arrangements into a one-dimensional line:

$$M! / [\text{Product over } i f(e_i)!] \quad ((10)) \quad \text{where } M \text{ is the total number of particles in the system}$$

These particles, however, obey the scattering rule: $\ln(g(e_i)) = -(e_i - u)/T$.

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one varies the \ln of ((10)) with respect to f subject to the constraint $-(e_i - u)/T f(e_i)$. The derivative d/df essentially represents a change in $f(e_i)$, but this may be thought of as a change in the number of particles associated with e_i . The form ((6)) which appears in statistical mechanics texts for systems in an ensemble makes this clearer.

The state e_i , however, gains or loses a particle through a scattering reaction and so enhancement or restriction rules related to the reaction need to be considered. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, there are no such rules, but for fermions and bosons, there are. Thus, we argue that one may not take a usual derivative. Rather, one must consider the probability of a system in equilibrium with $f(e_i)$ values and consider a reaction occurring (subject to constraints on energy and particle number) such that each $f(e_i)$ increases by 1.

The rule for a scattering reaction follows from:

$g(f)/f * f = -(e_i - u)/T \quad ((1))$ we use $1/f$ and f because " f " represents the Maxwell-Boltzmann (i.e. a physical density scattering rate) scenario and $g(f)/f$ any enhancement or restriction. For fermions $g(f)/f = 1/(1-f)$ and for bosons $1/(1+f)$.

Next, we use ((8)) or ((10)) as a base. Both represent "physical configurations". A particle shall be added to each $f(e_i)$ subject to constraints which in the form of ((8)) become:

$$\text{Exp}[\ln(g(f)/f)] \quad ((12))$$

We call "entropy" the power of the exponential. Its key terms are $[\ln(g(f)/f)]$ and $f \ln(f)$. Thus:

$$\text{Entropy}(f(e_i)+1) - \text{Entropy}(f(e_i)) = -(e_i-u)/T \quad ((13))$$

For each e_i :

$$\ln[g(f(e_i)+1)/(f(e_i)+1)] + [f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{after}} - [f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{before}} = -(e_i-u)/T \quad ((14))$$

$$[f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{after}} - [f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{before}} = d/df [f \ln(f)] = 1 + \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((15))$$

In ((15)), the ordinary derivative d/df is used because the factor $\ln(g/f)$ has already been included.

Thus, ((14)) may be solved using ((15)). For the case of bosons, $g(f(e_i)+1)/(f(e_i)+1) = 1/(f(e_i)+1)$

Note: $g(f(e_i)) = f/(1+f)$ for bosons assuming that an extra particle is added.

so ((14)) becomes:

$$-\ln(f+1) + 1 + \ln(f(e_i)) = -(e_i-u)/T \quad \text{or} \quad f = 1/[1-\exp((e-u)/T)] \quad \text{the BE distribution.} \quad ((16))$$

We have incorporated the "1" into u/T .

Thus, we argue that by incorporating scattering rules and the using the configuration arrangement ((10)), i.e. by using a different way of taking a derivative during maximization, one may obtain general equilibrium distributions without the need for factorial schemes.

By using the generalized derivative, we have not given a full expression for entropy, as Kaniadakis does, but we try to separate dynamical (reaction related) features from configuration ones i.e. $f \ln(f)$. This is very similar to the approach of treating $g(f(e_i))$ as a scattering probability and applying $M!/[m_1! m_2! \dots]$ to it and maximizing subject to number and energy constraints (as done in a previous note).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the only factorial scheme needed is $M!/[m_1! M_2! \dots]$ where $m_i =$ the number of particles with energy e_i . This represents physical configurations mapped into a straight line. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, one may maximize the \ln of this subject to the constraint $(e_i-u)/T f(e_i)$ using d/df . For more complicated cases, one may use:

$$\ln[g(f(e_i)+1)/(f(e_i)+1)] + [f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{after}} - [f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{before}} = -(e_i-u)/T$$

Where the first term describes the extra enhancement or restriction to the probability due to generalized scattering. For fermions it is $1/(1-f)$ and for bosons $1/(1+f)$.

$[f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{after}} - [f(e_i)\ln(f(e_i))]_{\text{before}}$ is given by $\ln(f(e_i))+1$.

Thus, one does not need special configuration factorial schemes for each special case, e.g. one for fermions, another for bosons etc. We argue that scattering rules are key and are directly involved in the process of maximizing probability. By using a generalized derivative, one may separate the dynamical effects of scattering from configuration effects. For example, if an extra particle is added to $f(e_1)$, there is a configuration effect because $1/f(e_1)!$ in the denominator of ((10)) changes, but for bosons and fermions, there is also an affect on scattering rates of reactions which involve e_1 .

References

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